

The Impact of Political Satire on the Level of Political Discourse and Civic Engagement among Selected Youth Leaders in the Province of Cavite

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ABSTRACT

In a democratic society where freedom of expression is constantly repressed, people devise ways to communicate criticisms towards the government. One of these is using satire. The use of political satire has flourished in Philippine contemporary politics. It strives to attack the absurdity of society and politics creatively. Through the expansion of mass media, satire has been utilized to disseminate political information and as an avenue for activism.

This study investigated the impact of political satire on political discourse and civic engagement among selected youth leaders in the province of Cavite. This study determined the following: (1) types of political satire media strategies the participants are frequently exposed to; (2) their level of exposure to these media strategies; (3) their level of political discourse; (4) their level of civic engagement; and (5) examined if exposure to political satire media strategies could predict the level of political discourse and civic engagement. Responses from 391 youth leaders in Cavite were gathered. A descriptive-correlational analysis has been applied to identify the relationship between variables.

The result showed that the exposure to different political satire media strategies has a significant positive relationship with the level of political discourse and civic engagement. An increase in exposure tends to increase the level of political discourse and civic engagement. It implies that political satire has a great potential as an unconventional way to spread information and encourage the mass to engage in politics. Satire has a positive impact to ignite discussion and generate active citizen participation.

Keywords: *satire; political discourse; civic engagement; youth leaders; media*

INTRODUCTION

Aside from entertainment, political satire has been used as a strategy against oppression, a call for action, and means to effectively dispense information to the masses. It became an avenue for socio-political criticism and strives to attack the absurdity of society and politics in creative manner.

In western-democratic societies, the use of political satire is considered as legitimate source of information. An analysis was published by Pew Research Center (2014) which stated that satirical news media such as The Daily Show and The Colbert Report are trusted by its viewers and considered them as part of their day-to-day news consumption. Lee (2012) stated that the use of political satire in media outlets promotes political engagement among the citizens, especially those who lack interest in acquiring political information, due to its humorous approach. It provokes discussion among the interested audience and shares educational information with others via interpersonal discourse and online interaction.

During the 2022 Philippine National Election, the use of political satire to mock electoral candidates is widely popular. Prominent news outlets such as Manila Bulletin and Philippine Star started to incorporate satire in presenting their news – which gained greater engagement from readers compared to their previous style of reporting. It stirs up political discussions among the netizens and enables ordinary people to express their opinion. Satire breaks the stereotype of politics perceived as complicated, tiresome, and intimidating – capturing the taste of the masses. Contrary to its positive attributions, political satire has been used by different political actors as a form of propaganda. Adams (2018) claimed that numerous websites claimed that they are satirical but intend to cause mis- and disinformation among their audience. The problem arises when satirical information was thought to be a fact by its readers and shared as part of serious political discussion. These kinds of materials that aim to be deceptive were mostly difficult to spot for most people. If this information continuously circulates in the political sphere, it can negatively affect the democratic process. Plevriti (2014) postulated that political memes only satirize politics. They aim to be humorous, but critical assessment of recent political issues is often overlooked and not taken seriously. According to Declercq (2018), the use of satire can be associated with being unpatriotic and rebellious. Hence, the big question is: Does political satire have the capability of democratizing and mobilizing a nation, or a gradual democratic deterioration?

Due to contradicting statements on the effect of political satire, the researchers intend to clarify these inconsistencies. Also, the researchers found that most of the academic data on the utilization of political satire were international studies. There is little to no research on the local arena about the relationship of satire with political discourse and civic engagement. The researchers aim to identify the different political satire media strategies used by the selected youth leaders in the province of Cavite. This study measures the impact of political satire on their level of political discourse and civic engagement.

Research Questions

Generally, the study determined the impact of political satire on the level of political discourse and civic engagement among selected youth leaders in the province of Cavite.

Specifically, the study identified the following:

1. What type of political satire media strategies do participants are frequently exposed to?
2. What is the level of exposure of the participants to different political satire media strategies?
3. What is the level of political discourse of the participants?
4. What is the level of civic engagement of the participants?
5. Does exposure to political satire media strategies significantly predict the level of political discourse and level of civic engagement of the participants?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers conducted a Descriptive research study with a Quantitative-Correlational approach to answer the research questions and analyze the data. The quantitative method helped the researchers determine the strength of the relationship between the level of exposure to different political satire media strategies, level of political discourse, and level of civic engagement.

The researchers applied Purposive-Criterion Sampling, a type of non-probability sampling. It helped the researchers to choose the participants that provided substantial data for the study. Seventeen (17) youth leaders were chosen among the twenty-three (23) municipalities and cities in the province of Cavite. A total of three-hundred ninety-one (391) responses from youth leaders in the province were gathered.

The data was collected through the use of self-made questionnaire. Data gathering was conducted from third week of February to first of March 2023 via face-to-face interaction and online method such as google form. The collected data was analyzed and interpreted by a licensed statistician in the university using mean, standard deviation, and linear regression analysis.

RESULTS

Political Satire Media Strategies

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage of different political satire media strategies that participants frequently encountered. Majority of the participants, 358 or 92%, were exposed to political memes. This is followed by online videos with 313 or 80% of the responses. While 67% or 263 participants answered that they were also exposed to films that contain political satire. Caricatures and literary pieces got low responses which are 29% and 28% respectively.

Table 1. Different types of political satire media strategies where the youth leaders are frequently exposed to. (n=391)

POLITICAL SATIRE MEDIA STRATEGIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Political Memes	358	92%
Online Videos	313	80%
Film	263	67%
TV Shows	224	57%
Comic Strips	175	45%

Commentary	152	39%
Stand-up Comedian	152	39%
Podcasts	145	37%
Cartoons	119	30%
Caricatures	113	29%
Literary Pieces	110	28%

Level of Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies

Table 2 shows the measure of central tendency for exposure to different political satire media strategies using the mean and the standard deviation. The results unfolded that Statement No. 1 got the highest mean score at 3.49. It indicates that they are moderately exposed and often encounter political satire through different platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, television, etc.

On the other hand, Statement No. 6 has the lowest mean score of 2.47, which means that the participants are slightly exposed to cartoons containing political satire. They had been exposed to a minimal amount of the medium, but not too often.

The overall mean score of 2.87 suggested that the participants are moderately exposed to different political satire media strategies. It indicates that youth leaders are exposed to a good amount of political satire through different media but not frequently.

Table 2. Measures of central tendency for exposure to different political satire media strategies

INDICATORS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. I encounter political satire on a daily basis through Facebook, Twitter, Tiktok, Television, and in other media.	3.49	0.60	Highly Exposed
2. I am watching comedic films/TV shows that subtly discuss politics hilariously.	2.82	0.79	Moderately Exposed
3. I read posts online / literary pieces that depict societal condition in humorous manner.	3.17	0.79	Moderately Exposed
4. I watch stand-up comedian performances that make fun of infamous corrupt politicians.	2.60	0.93	Moderately Exposed
5. I see caricatures on newspapers (traditional or digital) that ridicules and criticizes the government.	2.76	0.91	Moderately Exposed
6. I watch cartoon/s that has political satire in it.	2.47	0.97	Slightly Exposed
7. I am listening to podcasts that tackles political and social issues in satirical tone.	2.51	0.97	Moderately Exposed
8. I see comics [traditional/digital] that mock elected officials when they commit unwise decisions.	2.89	0.95	Moderately Exposed
9. I am watching online videos containing political parody.	3.03	0.87	Moderately Exposed

10. I choose to watch videos that tackle politics in satirical manner.	2.73	0.90	Moderately Exposed
11. My social media timeline contains different political satire media strategies.	3.02	0.92	Moderately Exposed
12. I listen to commentaries that tackle government's negligence in humorous way.	2.71	0.92	Moderately Exposed
13. I see political memes when I am using my social media.	3.47	0.70	Highly Exposed
14. I am a follower of social media pages which posts imply political satire.	2.72	1.07	Moderately Exposed
15. I am a follower of various personalities that often share their political beliefs in satirical manner.	2.68	1.04	Moderately Exposed
Overall	2.87	0.62	Moderately Exposed

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/Highly Exposed
2.50-3.24 Often/Moderately Exposed
1.75-2.49 Rarely/Slightly Exposed
1.0-1.74 Never/Not Exposed

Level of Political Discourse

Table 3 presented the measures of central tendency for level of political discourse using the mean and the standard deviation. The analysis showed that statement nos. 4 and 10 got the highest mean score at 3.18. This indicates that the participants explain their thoughts calmly even though they disagree with another person's way of thinking and most of them are often conversing with their colleagues about the solutions to the problems in their organization or community. While statement no. 8 got the lowest. It means that most of them rarely talk to politicians to raise their organization's or community's concern.

The overall mean score of the items that measured the level of political discourse of the participants was 2.81. It indicates that the participants are moderately engaged in political discourse. They are engaging in discussions about politics, but not frequently.

Table 3. Measures of central tendency for level of political discourse

INDICATORS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. I am joining online political discussions through commenting on social media posts (Facebook, Twitter, Tiktok, Quora, etc.).	2.40	0.98	Slightly Engaged
2. I discuss political information with my friends and family members.	3.17	0.81	Moderately Engaged
3. I share my thoughts about politics by posting online (Facebook, Twitter, Tiktok, Quora, etc.).	2.70	1.00	Moderately Engaged
4. When I disagree with the statement of another person regarding political issues, I try to share my stand calmly.	3.18	0.84	Moderately Engaged
5. I engage myself in debates and meetings in our organization/ community.	2.69	0.98	Moderately Engaged

6. I share my insights regarding public concerns in our organization/ community.	2.96	0.91	Moderately Engaged
7. I am joining seminars to gain political knowledge.	2.71	1.01	Moderately Engaged
8. I talk to local politicians to raise problems in our community that needs solutions.	2.15	1.02	Slightly Engaged
9. I share my sentiments regarding political matters.	2.95	0.90	Moderately Engaged
10. I am talking to my colleagues about the possible solutions to the problems in our organization/ community.	3.18	0.82	Moderately Engaged
11. I share my political stand to other people to persuade them towards challenging our political leaders to do their duties.	2.94	0.92	Moderately Engaged
12. Sharing my sentiments about politics is something ordinary to me.	2.91	0.91	Moderately Engaged
13. When talking to my friends, politics is a topic that I never forget to talk about.	2.69	0.98	Moderately Engaged
14. Joining political discussion excites me.	2.86	0.96	Moderately Engaged
15. I like attending debates relating to politics	2.62	1.02	Moderately Engaged
Overall	2.81	0.73	Moderately Engaged

Legend: 3.25-4.00	Always/Highly Engaged
2.50-3.24	Often/Moderately Engaged
1.75-2.49	Rarely/Slightly Engaged
1.0-1.74	Never/Not Engaged

Level of Civic Engagement

Table 4 exhibited the measure of central tendency for level of civic engagement. The descriptive analysis showed that statement no. 2 got the highest mean score of 3.17, followed by statement no. 3. These indicated that the youth leaders are making sure that they will be able to attend the meetings in their organization or community and they positively identified that they had been active participants of the electoral process. It also means that they did these activities three to five times in the span of 12 months. On the other side, parallel to table 3, statement no. 10 which is talking to politicians to raise a public concern or collaborate for a project got the lowest mean score at 2.09.

The overall mean score is at 2.71 which indicated that the youth leaders are moderately engaged in civic activities. Most of the youth leaders did these activities at least three times within the last 12 months.

Table 4. Measures of central tendency for level of civic engagement

INDICATORS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. I follow/ followed and join/ joined a political campaign or organization.	2.68	1.05	Moderately Engaged

2. I make/ made sure that I attend/ attended each meeting in our organization/ community.	3.17	0.96	Moderately Engaged
3. I sign/ signed a petition that I know will be beneficial to the community.	2.93	1.02	Moderately Engaged
4. I make/ made social media posts for political issues that are important to me.	2.72	1.06	Moderately Engaged
5. I join/ joined public rally or protest to support an electoral candidate or an advocacy.	2.35	1.14	Slightly Engaged
6. I avoid/ avoided purchasing something as a form of protest; or I actively purchase/ purchased something to support an advocacy.	2.56	1.11	Moderately Engaged
7. I volunteer/ volunteered for a group or cause.	2.88	1.00	Moderately Engaged
8. I urge/ urged others to get politically involved on Facebook, Twitter, and other social media platforms.	2.53	1.07	Moderately Engaged
9. I donate/ donated to a campaign or cause.	2.60	1.05	Moderately Engaged
10. I contact/ contacted an elected official to raise a public concern or to collaborate for a community project.	2.09	1.07	Moderately Engaged
11. I join/ joined clean-up drive/s.	2.62	1.04	Moderately Engaged
12. I join/ joined a non-profitable organization.	2.70	1.09	Moderately Engaged
13. I participate/ participated in election process: national elections, senatorial elections, local elections, school/university elections, etc.	3.15	1.01	Moderately Engaged
14. I actively campaign/ campaigned for an electoral candidate.	2.77	1.06	Moderately Engaged
15. I participate/ participated in organizing a fund-raising activity for a cause.	2.87	1.00	Moderately Engaged
Overall	2.71	0.74	Moderately Engaged

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/Highly Engaged – participated in the activity more than 5 times within the last 12 months
2.50-3.24 Often/Moderately Engaged – participated 3-5 times within the last 12 months
1.75-2.49 Rarely/Slightly Engaged – participated 1-2 times within the last 12 months
1.0-1.74 Never/Not Engage – Haven’t done it

Relationship of Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies to Dependent Variables

A. As Predictor of Political Discourse

The relationship between the level of exposure to political satire media strategies as predictor to the level of political discourse by using simple linear regression analysis was first

determined. Results suggest that the model predicts a significant amount of variability in the political discourse scores, $F(1,389) = 405.36$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = 0.51$. This means that 51% of the variability in political discourse scores can be explained by exposure to political satire media strategies. Specifically, an increase in the exposure to political satire media strategies tends to increase political discourse among the participants ($\beta = 0.71$, $t = 20.13$, $p < .001$).

Table 5. Exposure to political satire media strategies as predictor of political discourse (n = 391)

Variable	B	β	SE	T	p
Constant	0.41	-	0.12	3.36	< .001
Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies	0.83	0.71	0.04	20.13	< .001

B. As Predictor of Civic Engagement

The relationship between the level of exposure to political satire media strategies as predictor to the level of civic engagement by using simple linear regression analysis was also determined. Results suggest that the model predicts a significant amount of variability in the civic engagement scores, $F(1,389) = 273.93$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = 0.41$. This means that 41% of the variability in civic engagement scores can be explained by exposure to political satire media strategies. Specifically, an increase in the exposure to political satire media strategies tends to increase civic engagement among the participants ($\beta = 0.64$, $t = 16.55$, $p < .001$).

Table 6. Exposure to political satire media strategies as predictor of civic engagement (n = 391)

Variable	B	β	SE	t	p
Constant	0.51	-	0.14	3.77	< .001
Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies	0.76	0.64	0.05	16.55	< .001

DISCUSSION

Political Satire Media Strategies

Political satire has been used to criticize people in power even during the ancient times. For instance, Aristophanes targeted the Athenian leaders and state offices through his play called the Babylonians. Even Indian cartoonists poked fun at the illustrations of Egyptian leaders. And over the years, different political satire media strategies have emerged because of technological advancements.

The figures above imply that the participants encounter most of political satire contents through political memes and online videos. These can be explained by the nature of the mentioned media strategies. In the present time called the digital age, technology plays a role in information dissemination. Both political memes and online videos are circulating in majority of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Tiktok. These platforms can be accessed for free – making it available to wider scope of patrons especially the younger generation. Political memes and online videos are then followed by film and TV shows which are aired in cinemas and free tv channels which can easily be watched by the masses. On the other hand, literary pieces got the least percentage. Compared to other media strategies, it is inherently much harder to find and costly. Since the age of digitalization plays a great factor, the

accessibility of the media strategies can be attributed to the frequent exposure of the participants to political satire.

Based on the report of Philippine Statistics Authority, most Filipino households owned cellular phones (86.8%) and television (79.9%) in 2019. Filipino youth, ages 10 to 30 years old, are exposed to mass media on a daily basis. Television, internet, and magazines were the top forms of mass media that they consume frequently. Internet was used more to surf social media than for research related activities. The data gathered to answer statement of the problem no. 1 validated the claims of the related literatures discussed in previous chapters.

Meme creation is an acceptable activity in every social media platform like Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, and other social media platforms today. Meme has the ability to passed down socio-cultural behaviors to the next generation. According to Shifman (2013), meme became part of the popular culture that were shared and imitated by internet users. And through the popularity of this kind of media strategy, political satire flourished in social media platforms in recent years (Piata, 2016). Internet users use memes to deliver their opinions about politics (Shifman, 2013). Sreekumar and Vadrevu (2013) believe that political memes can be used to raise awareness about political issues. In a journal released by De Leon and Ballesteros (2021), meme is a tool that could be used as propaganda to in order to manipulate citizen's way of thinking.

Level of Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies

Political satirical contents have the power to inform and entertain. Satirists saw its potential to stir up public opinion about different societal issues. One of the motivations of satirists in creating satirical contents is to raise awareness--creatively. Thus, it is not surprising that the young generation and even those people who were cynic about politics were more inclined to consume these materials.

These findings imply that the youth leaders have moderate exposure to political satire media strategies and the accessibility of these media in a digitalized era is a key factor. It affirms one of the theories used in this study which is the Normative Theory. This theory laid out the roles of mass media in a democratic society and how media holds responsibility to carry out open discussion on public affairs and empowering the public through information. The wide reach of media in carrying out political information in the form of satire is evident in the figures shown in the table as most of the participants answered 'often' and 'always' in the questions. The virality of political satire in different forms of media strategies can also be attributed to the current Digital Era. The age of digitalization paves way for a greater accessibility of the media strategies to the masses including the youth. Given the scale and scope of youth exposure with media strategies, which is foreseeable to grow more, these platforms have great potential to become legitimate and effective tools to inform young people on aspects of politics.

The combined results shown in the table supports the claims of McClennen (2012) and Young (2013). Both authors enunciate that the young generation is immersed in political satire contents and most consumers of political satire came from this age group. This behavior can be explained by an article made by Martinez (2019). He stated that the general public is inclined to patronize and consume political satire content because of its compelling and entertaining disposition. The humorous approach of political satire captures the attention of the viewers.

It can also be observed from the figures that the participants had the highest amount of exposure on political satire through the use of social media platforms. This is parallel to the

study of David (2013). He stated that Filipino youth are inclined in Information and Communications Technology (ICT). Their extensive use of ICT contributes to their level of exposure. Thus, explaining the participants' moderate exposure to good amount of political satire content. The findings in this study are also in line with the findings of a qualitative study conducted by Penney (2019). The study suggests that youth are exposed in political satire because sharing such content encourages solidarity among like-minded peers and helps the youth build their political identity.

Level of Political Discourse

The results supported the claims in the research article presented by Cabo (2018). Cabo presented that the Filipino youth are interested in politics. They possess critical views towards politicians and political situation in the country. However, it can be observed that statement no. 8 got the lowest mean score. The behavior of youth leaders to rarely talk to politicians in raising concerns can be backed by the report from the United Nations Development Programme. Youth from Asia Pacific has low trust rate towards legislative and executive institutions. As stated by Goudie (2018), factors like distrust towards political institutions can also be the underlying factor.

Overall, the participants who are youth leaders in Cavite have been moderately engaged in political discourse. This result is in contrast with the report from National Youth Commission in 2010. Their report shows that Filipino youth avoids becoming an initiator on political issues – the table above shows otherwise.

Therefore, these findings imply that the youth leaders in Cavite are relatively active when it comes to political discourse, but not on an extensive level. The participants display positive attitude towards voicing out their political views. However, their level of political discourse does not reach the highest possible mean score. They are not highly engaged in political discourse considering they hold high position as officers in their respective council or group. Although they are in a democratic state which encourages freedom of speech and political participation, obstruction from their full civic potential may still occur.

Level of Civic Engagement

The results validated the claim in the study presented by Palomares, *et al.* (2021) that focused on the political participation among elected youth leaders specifically Sanggunian Kabataan officials. The results of their study show that their participants have an average to high levels of political participation. It is similar to the result in this study which determines that the selected youth leaders in Cavite are moderately exposed in participating in civic engagements. The result also proves the claim of the Commission on Elections in 2022 that youth are considered prime movers in civic activities like elections. Similar to the previous discussion under Table 3, this result is in contrast with the report from National Youth Commission in 2010. Their report shows that Filipino youth avoids becoming an initiator on political issues – the table above shows otherwise. Filipino youth leaders engage in different activities that has direct and indirect contribution in their community or respective group.

Therefore, these findings imply that the youth leaders in Cavite are relatively active in participating in various civic engagement activities, but not on an extensive level. The participants display positive attitude towards participating in the political process. However, their level of civic engagement does not reach the highest possible mean score. It can be inferred that the participants are more active in participating within the circle of their organization and

through informal participation. This observation can be explained through the previously identified obstacles to youth participation. They are not highly engaged in civic activities considering they hold high position as officers in their respective council or group. Although they are in a democratic state which encourages freedom of speech and political participation, obstruction from their full civic potential may still occur.

Relationship of Exposure to Political Satire Media Strategies to Dependent Variables

A. As Predictor of Political Discourse

The result validated the statement made by Plevriti (2013) in his dissertation. Satirists create satirical contents to generate commentaries that could stir up a discourse among its audience (Plevriti, 2013). The general public utilize the ability of political satire to voice out their opinions about politics. In addition, Martinez (2019) stated that the entertaining factor of political satire catches the attention of the people from different walks of life including those who lacks interest in politics. A study was conducted by Coronel, *et al.* (2020), the authors stipulated that people can easily retain information if it was delivered humorously. This is because the information was presented on the level of their understanding, hence retention of the information became easier. As a result, the consumers of the medium tend to share this information since they are more confident that they can explain it casually.

The integration of political satire in commentaries and discussions become a vibrant source of political information, and eventually shape public opinions through the use of social media. Meaningful discussions in the platform, as well as senseless political debates took place (Hapal, 2019). Since political information dissemination normalized the use of political satire on the internet, people became saturated with the medium. It introduced the masses to acquisition of political knowledge with an entertaining approach and with less mental effort while being engaged in politics. Abdel-raheem (2018) postulated that despite its divisive takes on certain issues, it became a norm and was well-accepted by its target audience.

The result implies that the exposure to political satire media is a significant predictor of political discourse among selected youth leaders in Cavite. This result validates one of the theories used in this study which is the Rational Choice Theory and supports the study of Lawrason (2015) – who also use the same theory. The Rational Choice Theory emphasizes how a person weighs the cost and benefit before committing a decision. In the study of Lawrason, she claimed that students patronize political comedy instead of hard news sources, yet unintentionally still acquiring the substantial political information. The time spent and attention exerted to acquire information serve as the cost, while the political information that has been gained serves as a benefit (Lawrason, 2015).

In this current study, the finding of Lawrason has been supported. Participants still acquire the political information they need even though it is through political satire contents. Participants has moderate exposure to political satire media strategies has also moderate level of engagement in political discourse. It can be inferred that frequent exposure to political satire bears a good benefit in terms of acquiring political information.

The result clearly showed that political satire is an effective tool to engage people in political discourse. People will engage in political discourse more frequently as a result of increased exposure to various political satire media strategies. Satirists are here to balance the wit and seriousness of politics. The role of political satire in political discussion is to make politics

inclusive despite having differences in societal or economic standing. Having citizens who are politically aware and knowledgeable is a necessity to maintain vibrant democracy. The utilization of political satire in different media is an efficient way to activate the citizens as focal agents of the democratic process.

People who employ political satire to show their dismay about the political condition in the country shall not be condemned. They are actually helping the masses to have access to information that is deemed to be understood by the few—mainly because of many indifferences. Moreover, this analysis also stressed it does not mean that one must believe every narrative they see. The result encourages the citizens to be radical, and to rationalize their thought process before putting it out for the public to consume. This analysis thus confirms that political satire is no longer just a joke about politics but could actually start meaningful discourses.

B. As Predictor of Civic Engagement

The result contrasts with the information presented by Allaina Kilby (2014) and Li Shao and Dongshu Liu (2018), that shows association between the variables. The result in this analysis suggests that exposure to different political satire media strategies has a significant relationship with civic engagement. Hoffman and Young (2011) emphasized that political satire has positive effects on civic engagement through an indirect route of political efficacy. Genuine forms of political satire such as political comedies are greatly associated with political participation. It implies that being exposed to political satirical content could foster the mobilization of people to generate political action (Baumgartner & Lockerbie, 2018). In fact, a study conducted by Kasirye (2019) validated the current analysis. They conducted a study to determine the association of political memes and political participation in Uganda. It posited that an individual is more likely to engage in activities involving politics if they are exposed to political satire. Zhang and Pinto (2021) stipulated that people who are exposed to memes have high levels of intention to protect our environment by joining activities that promote its conservation like clean up drives.

The result further implies that the exposure to political satire media is a significant predictor of civic engagement among selected youth leaders in Cavite. This result validates one of the theories used in this study which is the Affective Intelligence Theory or AIT. This theory emphasizes the role of emotions in generating participation. Political satire focuses not only on delivering political information but also touches the emotional side of individuals through its humorous nature. It has been proven in the study that the youth leaders' exposure and immersion to different political satire media strategies leads to their level of civic engagement. It can be inferred that the participants' reaction towards the political satire content that they encounter in different media urges them to become active in their community and become initiators of change.

Conclusions

This study seeks to broaden the understanding the impact of exposure to different political satire media strategies as it predicts the level of political discourse and civic engagement. Mass media, particularly, social media applications and sites greatly contributes to the popularization of political satire in recent years. Political satire is introduced into this realm through memes,

online videos, and films. Because satirical contents are easier to understand, people tend to patronize it more than any other formal information sources such as news articles and journals.

One of the challenges that the discipline of Political Science faces is how to introduce politics to the masses without them getting intimidated. Some Filipinos no longer watch news, because they do not want to hear negativity – they became cynic. Some do not want to welcome new political information, because they perceive it as complicated. Others are too busy and have no time to read lengthy news. All these that have been mentioned kill the democratic process.

In utilizing political satire, it delivers news and political information in a creative manner. Politics turn into bite sizes. It breaks the stereotype of politics perceived as complicated, tiresome, and intimidating – capturing the taste of the masses. The utilization of wit in delivering one's message has encouraged the citizens to be politically vocal. In other words, those who consume political satirical content tend to be more confident to share information because of the knowledge that they acquire from these materials. Thus, this explains why being exposed to different political satire media strategies tends to increase one's level of engagement in political discourse.

However, due to this political activity, it is not surprising that the spread of mis- and disinformation in the Philippines became extensive. To counter this, a pool of related literature and studies have found that satirists are using satire to unmask the truth that has been forcibly tainted using the same strategy. As a result, people from different spectrums of political ideology are creating rounds of discussions and debates about current political issues.

With regards to the effects of exposure to political satire media strategies on the level of civic engagement, this study shows that being exposed to the medium can intensify one's level of engagement in civic activities. Although this is the case, it is noticeable that youth leaders in Cavite have thin acts of civic engagement.

Attending meetings and participating in the election process are fundamentals and expected behaviors of being a youth leader. One cannot argue that these actions are essential part of democracy and clear manifestations that our country upholds the rights of its citizens granted by the Constitution. Having peaceful meetings indicates the right to assembly and being able to cast a vote shows one's right to suffrage. Yet, those civic activities that could directly affect communities such as participating in clean-up drives, joining non-government organizations, and giving donations, got lower values. But due to the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the result become acceptable. It vehemently chained the whole of humanity into the corners of our house. Insofar, these remarks cannot obliterate the fact that this study proves that being exposed to different political satire media strategies is a novel way that can bolster one's civic engagement.

This study positively affirms that political satire is a catalyst and can manifest change in democratic societies. Still, empirical studies on the effects of political satire and how it affects our democratic process need to be continuously conducted.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are raised by the researchers:

One of the several challenges that the researchers faced during the conduct of the study is the limited number of active youth leaders in each area of the province. By this, it is recommended that the future researchers may expand the study's scope. This study may be conducted and replicated in other provinces. Focusing on different age group or demographics of the participants is highly encouraged.

Another challenge that has been identified is the lack of complexity of the gathered data. Since the study is done quantitatively, the researchers did not have the chance to raise follow up questions to further investigate the participants' answers. It is highly encouraged by the researchers to employ a mixed method to conduct an in-depth analysis of the topic. An experimental study can also be used to differentiate the impacts of viewing news—or any other information source with a formal approach and political satire materials—on the consumers' knowledge retention and level of political understanding. This might be accomplished by showing them a video of both strategy and then administering a survey to them after they have watched it.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical principles set by the Cavite State University, the American Psychological Association, and the jurisdiction of Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 were followed while conducting this research study.

In writing this study, specifically in assembling the related literatures, all the ideas and concepts that the researchers acquired from these sources were properly cited. The researchers strictly validated that this paper is free from plagiarism of any kind. Fabrication for personal gain of the obtained information was not utilized; the researchers gave credit to where it is due.

This study is non-experimental and did not utilize human subjects. It was performed by seeking permission and approval from the university, participants, respective focal persons, and chairpersons of the collaborating organizations and institutions.

The gathering of data from the participants was handled with the outmost confidentiality and integrity. A consent form was attached to the questionnaire, the process did not begin until the participants gave their consent. The participants were allowed to refuse to participate or even withdraw their participation once it has started. All the participants voluntarily agreed to be part of the study. The participants were also permitted to ask questions and clarify things related to the study to the researchers.

During the data analysis, the identities of the participants and their personal information were undisclosed. Blind tallying and codes to secure privacy and maintain the anonymity of the participants were used. The data that were collected are kept securely within the property of the researchers. The information was bound for research purposes only. Since this study was already done, permanent termination of data was applied. All the encoded data were deleted in the hard drive of the researcher's device. The questionnaire sheets bearing the actual name of the participants were disposed through a manual paper shredder. The questionnaires bearing

the participants' information were terminated as a form of compliance with their legal obligation in securing the data.

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